

The Role of Christians Representatives in The First Jordanian Legislative Council 1929 – 1931 AD Historical Study

Ahmad Hamed Ibraheem AlQudah

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Abstract

This study tackles the role of Christians representatives in The First Jordanian Legislative Council based on the records of the council sessions. It focuses on their role in forming the reply to the, forming the inner procedure rules of the legislative council and obtaining the parliament immunity. It also looks at their position from the Jordanian – British treaty in 1928, and from Representatives and Amending the Basic Law.

Introduction

The year 1928, witnessed a remarkable event in the history of the legislative life in the Emirate of trans-Jordan, as the British Mandate Government reactivated the election law of the legislative council after suspending it for two years in 1923 and 1926. This was regarded as a subsequent step to the ratification of the Jordanian-British treaty signed in February 20, 1928 and in issuing the Basic law in April 16, 1928 which organized the legislative life. According to article (25), the legislative power was entrusted to the Prince and the legislative council, which consisted of elected representatives in accordance with the election law, in addition to the executive council, which consisted of five members appointed by the Prince based on the council chairman recommendations. On this basis, Hassan Khalid Abu-Al Huda initiated the publication of the legislative council election law in June 17, 1928. According to this law, the Emirate was divided into four electoral districts: Ajloun, Belqa, Karak and Maen. Christians representation was taken into consideration, so one seat was reserved in Belqa, Ajloun and Karak districts. Despite the opposition to the election law and the call for a boycott, the elections were held on January and February 1929. The council consisted of twenty-two members, sixteen of them were elected in accordance with the law and the six other were government members: five ministers and the prime minister who was also the chairman of the council.

There haven't been any studies, as far as I have researched, focusing on Jordanian Christians or trying to reveal their role in the emergence of Modern Jordan or their position from the political events yet. The importance of this study raises from the fact that it is trying to identify the role of the Jordanian Christians in the first legislative council: Najib Abu Shaar, Awdah Al- Qusous, and Bakhit Al-Ibrahim.

This study focuses on their role in wording the reply to the royal speech, setting up the inner procedure rules of the legislative council, obtaining the parliamentary immunity, their position to the Jordanian – British treaty 1928, amending the basic law.

This study relies mainly on the records of the first legislative council which are 83 sessions record. They were manuscript and numbered starting with the first session held in April, 2 1929 to the thirty first session held in August, 30 1929 later, they were published in the Official Gazette as an annex (1) in March, 1 1930.

First: The Christians Representatives and Setting Up the Inner Procedure Rules of the Legislative Council – During the First Session

The prime minister proposed forming one committee to review the treaty and to prepare the council inner procedure rules. This proposal was opposed by Najib Abu Al-Shaar, who suggested forming two separated committees, one to review the treaty and the other to prepare the council inner procedure rules. The member of the council approved on this proposal.(first session: 2 April ,1929 P.1)

Najib Abu Al-Shaar, Awdah Al-Qusous and Bakhit Al-Ibrahim agreed to elect the members of the committee by secret ballot. Because of the importance of the inner procedure rules in organizing the council duties and

sessions, Najib Abu Al-Shaer proposed forming nine-member-committee. The council members agreed on the proposal and nine members were elected. Najib Abu Shaer and Awdah Al-Qusous were among them.

The draft of the inner procedure rules was discussed by the legislative council members in more than one session. The members made sure that rules of inner procedure were adopted through agreeing to discuss the articles which were prepared by committee directly without waiting for the completion of all articles .(fourth session :10 April, 1929 P.9)

All the articles presented in the fifth session from (1 – 19) were adopted without any opposition except for a call to delete the second article ‘‘ provided that the chairman presided over the council, and in his absence a person appointed by the chairman ‘’. Awdah Al – Qusous was among the callers of deletion, based on the fact that the session can’t be opened except with a royal will and the presence of the government members. (fifth session: 14 April, 1929, P.12).

In addition, there was a demand for an amendment to article (16) regarding the permission to a member to the part of more than one committee. Najib Abu-Shaar proposed adding a sentence ‘‘ if the circumstance required that the members can be part in more than one committee ‘’ however, the council members voted to approve on this article without amendment. (fifth session 14 April, 1929 P.14).

In the same session, the government tried to proceed with adopting the remain articles prepared by the committee (20 – 46). However, the members of the council agreed on Shaim Aldin proposal to postpone considering these article until the upcoming session (fifth session P.12)

During the sixth session, Awdah Al-Qusous suggested that what was included in the Basic Law should not be included in the inner procedure code, because the Basic Law has been drafted and ratified, and the legislative council has no right to amend it. Najib Abu Al-Shaar supported this suggestion. (Sixth session : 17 April, 1929, P15). Therefore, he called for the elimination of article (19) from the inner procedure code because it is identical to article (37) from the Basic Law which states ‘‘ Each law draft should be presented by the prime minister or chairman of the department to the council as well as the annual budget ‘’ (Al-Sharq Al-Arabi: N.188,P7).

During the discussion of the inner procedure rules, Ibrahim Hashim requested postponing the voting on article (21) until the discussion of the following three articles. This request was opposed by the council members, including Najib Abu Al-Shaar, so Ibrahim Hashim was obliged to present the above mentioned article ‘‘After the period in question in the previous article has passed, the law draft is to be read publicly, then the first deliberation on the necessity of making this law should take place in general and not by considering each article separately, only after that the chairman of council can establish the agenda for the final opinions ‘’ (sixth session: P16)’’.

There was a discussion and controversy opinions among the members of the council about article 21. Awdeh Al Qusous opposed the idea of referring legal drafts that come from the government of members to the committee and he called for referring the legal drafts to the government (Sixth session P.16). However, Najib Abu Al-Shaar opposed Al-Qusous proposal demanding that legal draft that come from the government or the members should be referred to the committee. (Sixth session, P.16).

Articles 23, 43 related to the legal drafts, were also the focus of much debate and controversy among the members of the council. So, Al-Qusous repeated his calls to refer the members’ proposal to specialized departments to seek proper consultation regarding that (Sixth session: P 18 – 19) :

- The department chairman has the right to draft legal bills.
- The committee has the right to review.
- The final word is to given to the council regarding the ratification or amendment.

Najib Abu Al-Shaar opposed this proposal, and he confirmed the committee’s ability to draft legal bills taking into consideration the specialized departments consultation – when needed- without being present during the discussions (Sixth session: P 18 – 19).

During the inner procedure code discussion, the government was keen to amend the articles in the line with its interests, so during the seventh session Ibrahim Basha – the acting chairman – returned to Awdah Al-Qusous proposal about amending article (24), regarding referring the legal drafts to the department chairman (Seventh session: 21 April 1929, P 20).

Therefore, Najib Abu Al-Shaar expressed his strong disapproval of this proposal constitutionally because (Seventh session, P 20 – 21) :

- Article 37 of the constitution authorizes the council to draft legal bills.
- There is no provision in the constitution which states that the member’s proposal should be referred to the council chairman who would refer it to the department chairman.

After completing the inner procedure code deliberations, Ibrahim Hashim asked the council members to consider it before submitting it to the prince for the final approval. Najib Abu Al-Shaar requested that the inner procedure code should not be approved unless the immunity is provided and that his proposal is raised to voting. However, Ibrahim Hashim rejected this proposal, because the issue of immunity is not provided in the Basic Law (Eighth session: 22 April, 1929 P.28).

In the end, the council members agreed to submit the inner procedure code to Prince Abdullah along with the immunity request (Eighth session: P.30).

Hennery Cox was not satisfied with some of approved articles in the inner procedure code, so he requested from Hassan Khalid Abu Al-Huda meeting the Prince wishing that it wouldn't be approved according to article 33 from the Basic Law because it was incompatible with article (37) from the same Law (Al-Khataba, 2003, P 61 – 62). The Prince approved this request and returned the inner procedure code to the council. During the ninth session, the royal decree was read: “ your honorable chairman after reviewing the constitution we approve upon the inner procedure rules of the legislative council, with exception of articles 24 , 25 , 26 which we would like the higher council to consider them, so they would become compatible with article 37 of the Jordanian constitution (Ninth session : 24 April (1929 P.41).

Because of the importance of these articles in the inner procedure rules, Najib Abu Al-Shaar requested referring them to the committee. This request was voted on, which resulted in equal votes. The chairman favored not referring it on the committee (Ninth session: P 41, 43) :

- Article (24): During the council sessions, if one member or more presented a report proposing a law draft or requesting an amendment or the abolition of a certain law, then he must present a full report explaining his proposal. After reading this report, the chairman will raise it to a vote according to article (21) whether to accept the proposal or not.
- Article (25): if the proposal was accepted as mentioned in the above article, then it will be referred to the specialized department to organize the law draft and it must be sent to the council as soon as possible.
- Article (26) if one member noticed that the draft has been delayed and he was convinced that the time that had elapsed was sufficient enough to present it to the council, then he has the right to question the specialized department in accordance with sixth chapter of this procedure code.

Awdah Al-Qusous, Bakheet Al-Ibrahim and Najib Abu Al-Shaar requested printing and distributing the articles to the members within 24-hour duration to obtain opinions. (Ninth session: P 43 – 44).

After the deliberation on the governments amendments to the previous articles, the Christians representatives were divided between supporters and opponents to the Prince reply on these three articles. Awdah Al-Qusous affirmed that his royal highness has the authority – which is in the constitution – to approve or reject any law, also article (25) from the Basic Law provided the prince and the council with legislative authorities moreover, the proposals and law drafting should not be only codified with the council; because this indicate that the government is un-constitutional. (Tenth session: 28 April, 1929 P.46).

However, Najib Abu Al-Shaar opposed rejecting the three articles and he said: “ this reply doesn't bode well for the country “ and he requested that this topic should be subjected to in depth consideration before raising it to vote. He proposed referring the law drafts to the departments' chairmen must be time – bounded – and that draft is referred to the committee in case of delay from the department chairman during the specified time. (Tenth session, P 47 - 48).

He also suggested referring the legal drafts to the council chairman, and after approving them, they should be referred to the department chairman to please both parties. However, the council chairman rejected this proposal and clarified that this issue is related to specialty and it is not connected to the validity of Basic Law.

Najib Abu Al-Shaar replied “ there is no contradiction to the constitution and article (37) doesn't state that drafting laws is vested in the prime minister and the department chairman and the word (provide) can mean providing to the committee”. (Tenth session: P 51 – 52).

After considering these articles in depth, articles 24, 25, 26 were voted on, and they were approved by the majority. The royal decree was issued on April 29, 1929 with the ratification of these three articles in the form approved by the legislative council during the tenth session held on April 28, 1929, the inner procedure rules code was distributed to members (Twelfth session: 2 May, 1929 P.65).

Through these deliberations we can clearly see that the Christians representatives were divided over the referral of legal drafts that come from the government and the proposals presented from the council members:

- Najib Abu Al-Shaar believed in the committee role in the legislative council, and that law drafts that come from the government should be subjected to the legislative council supervision by referring them to the council which in turn refer them to the committee for deliberation.
- Owdeh Al-Qusous opposed this idea, he didn't believe that law drafts which come from the government should be referred to the committee for deliberations.

Second: The Christians Representatives and Parliamentary Immunity:

For the first legislative council members, the parliamentary immunity was a basic requirement especially when it wasn't mentioned in the Basic Law. In addition, the government insisted on approving the inner procedure rules without including the issue of immunity within the articles. “ we can't include in the inner procedure rules anything that wasn't mentioned in the basic law “. (Ninth session: 22 April, 1929. P.28).

The Christians representatives took advantage of the government's need to approve the inner procedure rules, so Najib Abu Al-Shaar demanded including the parliamentary immunity and raising it to vote. However, Ibrahim

Basha – the acting chairman – rejected this proposal. “ the issue would not be raised to vote and so you can contact his royal highness and after obtaining his approval, it can be discussed. ” because of the government insistence of not including immunity in the inner procedure code, Najib Abu Al-Shaar suggested submitting the code along with this issue of immunity (Ninth session: 22 April 1929, P28 – 30).

Bakhit Al-Ibrahim emphasized the importance of obtaining the parliamentary immunity: “ the importance of immunity raises from the need for freedom, I mean the council members are people with high merits and they haven’t committed a crime nor they will”. (Ninth session: 24 April, 1929 P.44).

Ibrahim Basha – the acting chairman – reminded the council members to reach out to the prince to be granted the parliamentary immunity. So, Said Al-Mufti suggested forming a committee to a company the chairman so they can request immunity from the price. So a committee, whose members included Najib Abu Al-Shaar, was elected. (Ninth session, P.44).

However, the government failed more than once to accompany the members of the committee to meet the price and ask for the immunity. This what Najib Abu Al-Shaar said “ regarding the immunity issue, Ibrahim Basha failed to meet his royal highness, immunity is necessary “. (Eleventh session: 30 April, 1929 P.61).

The Christians representatives also took advantage of the government need to ratify the Jordanian – British treaty and requested granting them parliamentary immunity. However, the government insisted on ratifying the treaty first because: (Eleventh session: P.59):

- The government is temporary unless the treaty is ratified.
- There isn’t any relation between the treaty and immunity.
- Immunity is not included in the Basic Law.

In front of the government rejection of granting the council members parliamentary immunity, Abu Al-Shaar criticized the government saying “ I noticed that there has been a division, the executive council took one side and the elected council took another side. This is a similar what Awdah Al-Qusous described as if we have a complainant and respondent and I feel sorry for that I want to register my objection; we fear the government though the executive council will be derived from the legislative council one day. I demand that the committee should address his royal highness considering the issue of immunity. “ (Eleventh session: P.61).

Tawfiq Abu Al-Huda enraged because of what Najib Abu Al-Shaar said and he replied to him saying “ Neither I nor anyone else is biased, and I feel sorry that he said that the executive council took one side, he is trying to separate between the council members “ (Eleventh session: P.61).

The council members insisted on granting them the parliamentary immunity to proceed with the procedure of ratifying the treaty. So, the council chairman declared: “ his royal highness issued the parliamentary immunity and it will be incorporated in the Basic Law “. (Eleventh session: P.62).

After the chairman statement, Tawfiq Abu Al-Huda suggested reading the treaty.

However, Najib Abu Al-Shaar requested raising the proposal for voting either reading the treaty or waiting for immunity to be granted. The majority (eleven votes) voted for reading the treaty. Awdah Al-Qusous was among the voters for reading the treaty, however he asserted on the importance of immunity:” immunity is a must but it is required that our work should not be disrupted pending that “ (Eleventh session, P. 62 – 63).

After the government success in ratifying the treaty on June, 4 1929, a publication was released modifying the Basic Law in June, 9 1929 in which the members of the legislative council were granted the parliamentary immunity. (Twenty-first session: 9, June, 1929, P.216: The official Gazette, N 230, P.2).

- A member of the legislative council shall not be arrested or tried during the session, unless the council is notified that there is a sufficient purpose for his trial or that he was arrested while committing a felony.
- Every member of the council is free to speak within the limits of the inner procedure rules approved by the council, and no legal procedures are taken against him for a vote or an opinion or a speech delivered during the council deliberations.
- If a member is arrested for some reason during the period in which the council is not convened, then the prime minister should inform the council with the taken procedures with necessary clarification.

Third: The Christians Representatives and the Jordanian – British treaty 1928.

The government had diligently endeavored to ratify the treaty, because article (20) requires that neither the government nor the council shall be recognized unless the treaty is ratified. Therefore, during the eleventh session the treaty was submitted to the council members and it was opened for proof reading, deliberations and expressing opinions. However, the council members were divided between supporters or opponents to reading the treaty or referring it to the committee. Awdah Al-Quous supported referring the treaty to the committee and he said “ it would be better if committees were formed and the treaty was referred to a specialized committee so it would receive proper investigation and an adequate record is delivered “ (Eleventh session: 30 April, 1929, P.59).

The government succeeded in obtaining the majority approval for reading the treaty, however Awdah Al-Qusous objected that there had been two translations provided for the treaty wondering which one was certified? The government clarified that the English version was approved (Eleventh session P.63). The

members of the council questioned the existence of two translated versions, so the government replied “ the first version was translated in Jerusalem and the second version was signed here in the presence of a council which included members who were proficient in English language. Several errors were found in the first version, so the prime minister went to Jerusalem and signed it there “ (Thirteenth session: 8 May 1929 P.88). Awdah Al-Qusous demanded that the council must be informed with the authentic version of the treaty; since the official Gazette published the erroneous version for comment” (Thirteenth session, P89).

During the fourteenth session, the government presented the Arabic and English versions to be contrasted. The Arabic version was read in the council, but Najib Abu Al-Shaar opposed reading the English version (Fourteenth session: 11 May, 1929 P.93). That meant that he demanded forming a committee for reviewing the treaty.

However, the government opposed forming a committee to review the treaty though it was satisfied with the nominated names chosen by Shamis Al-Din Sami to review the treaty during reading it in the council and they were: Halim Abu Rahma , Najib Abu Al-shaar , Awdah Al-Qusous. (fourteenth session P.94).

To pressure the government, the council members – including Najib Abu Al-Shaar and Awdah Al-Qusous – demanded raising the issue of forming a review committee for voting. However, Abu Al-Huda asserted the previous governmental refusal previous to this proposal suggesting that it would be sufficient reading it by members who are proficient in English language. (Fourteenth session: P. 94-95).

Najib Abu Al-Shaar proposed forming a committee to investigate the preceded negotiation that lead to the conclusion of the treaty and he explained his reasons: (Fourteenth session: P 69 – 98).

- The Jordanian people, through their representatives, were not aware of the parliamentary negotiations that took place between the political representatives that preceded the conclusion of this agreement.
- In case of variance in the interpretation of the agreement or one of its clauses, the two parties can be enlightened by checking the negotiators intentions.
- This agreement is subject to modification, and council members are under no obligation to ratify the treaty once it was signed by the negotiators.

After much discussions and debates between the government and the council members, the government approved on forming a committee to meet the price and seek explanations about the negotiations that preceded the conclusion of the treaty, in addition to a committee to review the translation of the treaty.

Among the elected committee members were the three Christians representatives: Najib Abu Al-Shaar , who received the higher number of votes (15 votes), Awdah Al-Qusous and Bakhit Al-Ibrahim who both received 8 Votes. The committee succeeded in the meeting the price. During the fifteenth session, Najib Al-Sharedh presented what the price mentioned about the stages before the signing the treaty and he asserted on the need to ratify the treaty rapidly. (Fifteenth session: 13 May, 1929, P 105 – 106).

Najib Abu Al-Shaar presented a brief report about the committee works which included Halim Bek Abu Rahma, Awdah Al-Qusous, and himself due to their knowledge of the English language to review the translated version of the treaty. He also mentioned that the committee sought the assistant of Sheikh Fuad Bek Al-Khatib.

The committee met over two days in May 12,13 1929 and they found some linguistic and typographical errors. (Fifteenth session: P 107 – 115).

After finalizing the committee work, Najib Abu Al-Shaar was the first speaker about the treaty. He explained its illegality due to the contradiction with some articles in the constitution: (Sixteenth session: 14 May, 1929 P 131, 134).

- Article 14 of this agreement authorizes her Majesty the Queen of England to declare martial law, while article 69 of the constitution authorizes his highness the prince.
- Article (17) of this agreement states that the prince agrees to follow the advice of her Majesty the Queen of England to award concessions and invest the natural resources, while article (68) of the constitution authorizes the prince to award concessions with a law issued by the legislative council.
- Article (21) states that in case of variance in the interpretation of any article in the treaty, then the English version is the reference without mentioning who would be responsible for the needed clarification whether it is his highness the prince or the British commissioner or a specialized mixed committee formed when needed.

Awdah Al-Qusous demanded approving the treaty in light of the allied countries betrayal to Arabs who took part in the First World War, so they will be granted full and complete independence (Sixth session: 14 May 1929, P 138 – 139). He also clarified the local position of the treaty, indicating that there were a division in the public opinions between people who supported and people who opposed the treaty. He praised the position of both parties which demonstrated loyalty and adherence to the rights of their country, he also clarified that it is his duty as a representative to review the treaty carefully and he reached the following conclusions: (Sixteenth session P.139 – 143).

- We are thankful for the British government for excluding Transjordan from the issue of establishing a national home for the Jewish people.

- The problem of Transjordan doesn't lie in the treaty, but in the mandate deed because most of its articles are copied from there.
- In case of rejection of the treaty, then Britain will apply the mandate Deed strictly and Britain will become the absolute authority in the country.

To conclude his speech, he called the council members to appeal to reason and for wisdom to prevail before approving or rejecting the treaty "let's appeal to reason and think carefully, what would be the disadvantages of ratifying the treaty and what would be the disadvantages of rejecting it, what will happen after rejecting it and what will happen after ratifying it, we should not be driven by factors of national enthusiasm and we shouldn't despair as well when we realize that the one standing against our national aspirations is not one government but several major countries and we have to choose the better of two evils" (Sixteenth session, P143).

As the council members concluded their deliberations about the treaty, Tawfiq Abu Al-Huda presented the governmental speech to reply to their observations. So, he praised Awdah Al-Qusous statement which described the situation in the Arab world after the First World War and how the allied countries reneged on their promises and didn't grant some countries their independence, and how he thanked the British government for excluding Transjordan from the national home land for Jewish people issue. He also confirmed what Awdah Al-Qusous and Najib Abu Al-Shaar mentioned that most of the treaty articles are taken from the Mandate Deed. (Seventeenth session: 27, May 1929 P 148 – 150).

At the end of his speech, Tawfiq Abu Al-Huda clarified that it would be better to ratify the treaty considering the circumstances in the country: "Gentlemen, this is the treaty and this is the situation. This treaty is not what the country truly needs, and it is even less than that, however, it seems to be better than the Mandate Deed and the absolute power. My brothers, there is a huge difference between being an independent country bounding itself with such treaty and between moving to more secure and independent country through using agreements."

Najib Abu Al-Shaar replied to government saying "this governmental reply is not sufficient and I agree with Alaa Aldin proposal to print the reply and hand it to members and we must be given enough time to study it". (Seventeenth session: P156).

After studying the government reply, fourteen members – including the three Christians Najib Abu Al-Shaar, Awdeh Al-Qusous and Bakhit Basha – proposed that the government have to negotiate the treaty terms with the mandate government to amend some of them especially those causing the disagreement, so treaty will become more compatible with the national sovereignty and the legitimate rights and these were: "the first article, the second paragraph from the second article, the fifth, the sixth, the seventh, and tenth articles, the second paragraph of the eleventh article, the fourteenth and sixteenth articles. (Eighteenth session: 30 May 1929 P.170).

Tawfiq Abu Al-Huda submitted the members' proposal to the British commissioner on June, 1 1929. The proposal was rejected but, amending the treaty could be possible after ratifying it from the legislative council (Nineteenth session: 1 June, 1929, P 182 – 183). The prime minister demanded the council to take decision either to ratify or reject it. Najib Abu Al-Shaar suggested postponing the voting until all the council members were informed with the British commissioner response. (Nineteenth session P 184).

During the twentieth session in June, 4 1929, which was held to consider the British commissioner reply, 15 members presented a memorandum to the prime minister declaring their agreement to ratify the treaty. Among these members, who were lobbied outside the council chamber to ratify the treaty, was Awdah Al-Quosus (twentieth session:4 June, 1929.p192-193):

- Fearing that the majority in the council would not ratify the treaty, especially after reading the memorandum presented by 14 members who agreed to ratify it provided that some of the article were amended.
- The British government refused making any amendments except after ratifying it from the legislative council as it is.

Najib Abu Al-Shaar criticized the 15 council members who agreed on ratifying the treaty. He then presented a long speech in which he mentioned the following points: (Twentieth session: 4 June, 1929, P 194 – 195).

- The rapid reply of the British commissioner to the memorandum submitted by the 14 members regarding the request to amend the treaty.
- The government refusal to negotiate amending the treaty with the British government and how this denotes its underestimating the nation's rights.
- The reply to the memorandum came from the British commissioner and not from the high commissioner in Palestine who is authorized to signed the treaty with the Jordanian government.

At the end of his speech, he stated his rejection of the treaty provided that it was amended according to the memorandum submitted by the 14 members of the council "..... It is our duty now to insist on the contents of the memorandum regarding amending the treaty in way that doesn't contradict with Britain vital interests and it is international commitments is our country, not insisting on these demands means that we are compromising,

hasting and surrendering. Grief and woe are destined to those who compromise the nation's rights especially when they are represented to defend them. ' (Twentieth session: P 195).

Bakhit Al-Ibrahim asserted on his rejection to ratify the treaty provided that it was amended in accordance with the 14 member's memorandum, because the treaty is unfair, unjust and harmful to the country's political and economic interests (Twentieth session P .208).

Based on the memorandum which declared the approval of 15 members to ratify the treaty, the council chairman raised the treaty to voting in accordance with article (41) of the inner procedure rules. Najib Abu Al-Shaar and Bakhit Al-Ibrahim withdrew from the session before voting, while Awdah Al-Qusous voted on ratifying the treaty. The result of votes was 15 members voted, 4 members withdrew and said Al-Mufity and Najib Abu Al-Shaar were absent. (Twentieth session: 4 June 1929, P 203 – 204).

Everyone who ratified the treaty was affected by Najib Abu Al-Shaar's speech when he said ' Grief and woe are destined to those who compromise the nation's rights especially when they are represented to defend them ' . Abdullah Al-Shareh defended the integrity of the 15 members, who ratified the treaty, and criticized Najib Abu Al-Shaar describing his position as childish and he raised doubts about his age accusing him of not reaching the legal age that entitles him to be a member in the council. (Twenty- first session: 9 June, 1929, P 211 – 212).

Najib Abu Al-Shaar replied to Abdullah Al-Shareh's speech: (Twenty- first session P, 213).

- The treaty was decided by the previous session, and the inner procedure rules don't allow discussing a finished issue.
- Regarding the age point, then it is outside the council's authority and it is connected with the registration officer's authority, who examined it and was convinced with the proof and documents from the courts about reaching the legal age.

Fourth: Christian Representatives and Amending the Basic Law:

Article 70 in the Basic Law states that: ' the prince may at any time, within two years from the date when this law was put in to effect, – while observing his obligations – to change or cancel or add any bill issued by any provision of this Basic Law to seek the intended purposes. He also may add any other necessary articles to the law ' (The official Gazette, no 188, P13).

The first amendment to the Basic Law was in June, 9 1929 in which the parliamentary immunity was added to article 41 under the pressure of the first legislative council members. The member's success in amending the Basic Law encouraged them to request further amendments to the Basic Law which was issued by the British mandate government in line with its interests in the region.

During the fourteenth session, which was held in December, 6 1930, thirteen members – including two Christian representatives Najib Abu Al-shaar and Bakhit Al-Ibrahim – suggested making amendments to some articles in the Basic Law and they are: (fourth session : 6 December 1930 , supplement to the official Gazette , No 35 , P 186).

- Amendments to article 21:
 - The executive council is composed of a chairman and five members, all or at least three of them are members of the legislative council, and two members from ministers and departments heads provided that the inauguration or dismissal of the chairman is carried out by the prince.
 - The chairman has to elect his colleagues from the homogeneous members. They share responsibility with them and if they fall, he falls. The administration of Transjordan affairs is entrusted to this council and they meet under the leadership of the prime minister to consider the country affairs. The prime minister raises the council's decisions to the prince to receive higher ratification.

This council can be tried jointly or individually in the case of committing a crime that affects the country's rights and this requires a special court formed in accordance with the prince's will. They also demanded amending the last paragraph of article (26) with: the legislative council term lasts for four years instead of three years. Also amending the third paragraph of article (32) with: in case that the chairman of the council hasn't appointed a deputy chairman, then the council is presided over by an elected member with the absolute majority of the council members' votes instead of being presided over by the most senior member of the legislative council who is not elected.

It was clear from the proposed amendments that the legislative council members – who submitted the proposal – aimed to:

- Transforming the executive council from an advisory council into a council of ministers with broad authorities to manage the country affairs.
- The designate prime minister chooses the ministers without interference from the prince and that there are members of the legislative council in the government.
- Hold the prime minister and the ministers accountable, in case they committed any constitutional or legal violations.

- Grant the legislative council the authority to elect the chairman deputy of the council in case that the chairman hasn't appointed one during his absence. Extending the term of the council from three years to four years, so modifying the council sessions to four in each year.

However, the government worked to abort these proposals, especially the one which grants the legislative council the authority to hold the ministers accountable and refer them to jurisdiction (fourteenth session: 6 December 1930, supplement to official Gazette, No. 35 P. 186 – 187):

- Requested from the secretary general of the government, Tawfiq Abu Al-Huda, to postpone the deliberations of the proposal based on article 7 of the inner procedure rules which states that each proposal must be submitted five days before the scheduled deliberation day.
- Requested from prime minister to be careful, not to be in a hurry and to take his time; because the proposal is important and affects the legislation, national sovereignty and administrative conditions in the country.

Najib Abu Al-shaar replied to the government's demands with a statement in which he confirmed the validity of what Tawfiq Abu Al-Huda mentioned and clarified to him and to the council members that article 20 of inner procedure rules authorizes the council to consider any proposal or bill at once. He requested the council members to: to acknowledge in the first place the necessity to discuss the proposal due to its importance (fourteenth session: 6 December 1930, P 186 – 187). Due to the insistence of Najib Abu Al-Shaar and some of the council members to discuss the proposal of amending the Basic Law, the council chairman proposed postponing the consideration of this proposal, and the council members agreed (fourteenth session: 6 December 1930, P 187).

During session (18) held in December 15, 1930, the proposal of amending the Basic Law wasn't among the scheduled topics of the session. So, Najib suggested conducting the deliberations during the same session, especially since it was signed by two thirds of the elected council members and more than five days had passed since it was printed and distributed. However, the government rejected Najib Abu Al-Shaar request. (Eighteenth session: 15 December, 1930, supplement to the official Gazette, No 39, P220).

Abu – Shaar returned and offered the government to postpone considering it and raised it to deliberation, however the government rejected this proposal as well. In front of the government's delay in the discussing the proposal of amending the Basic Law, Najib Abu Al-Shaar declared his intention to proceed with his demand to amend the Basic Law in front of the council members and he said “ I any ways, I can't withdraw my proposal, and I have collected the opinions of my honorable colleagues whom the majority approved it, unless that they have changed their minds ” (Eighteenth session: 15 December 1930 P.221).

The government postponed the discussion of the proposal during the nineteenth session again due to lack of time and also during the twentieth session, because the council rejected considering it as a main topic for the session. (Nineteen session: 20 December 1930, supplement to the official Gazette, No 40 P.240: Twentieth session: 22 December 1930, supplement to the official Gazette, No 41, P242).

The government's delay in discussing the proposal sparked Shams Al-Din Sami, who requested from the government reading it for reference; because the delay in discussing it, would force the council to postpone it for the next third regular session. The council then agreed to read it by the majority. (Twenty first session: 31 December 1930, supplement to the official Gazette, no 42 P 251).

After the council agreement on reading the proposed amendments to the Basic Law, Najib Abu Al-Shaar requested that the laws interpretation committee should base its work, while wording the proposal amendments, to the Basic Law on the following basis (Twenty – first session: 31 December 1930, P 251, 252):

- The text has to be consistent with the idea of forming a responsible government in the country in accordance with what was stated in the first paragraph.
- Extending the term of the council from three to four years to save the people the trouble of elections.
- The trial of ministers in accordance with what was stated in the third paragraph.

Awdeh Al – Qusous presented a length statement in which he clarified that the aim of these amendments is to broaden the council and the government authorities, so it will become a responsible government just like the civilized governments of the world. He also explained the difficulty of the government's approval of it “ I have to thank them and share these wishes and hopes ” (Twenty – first session: 31 December 1930, P 252).

He also affirmed his support for the proposal to amend the Basic Law provided that it is not bounded by the proposal submitted by 13 members, because it is fragmented according to his description.

In order to reach the goals of the amendments, he suggested that council members have to ask the government to formulate the Basic Law in an adequate manner to transform the government council into a council of ministers similar to the constitutional governments in other countries. He also requested granting the council the right to vote of confidence to the government, to broaden the council authorities and oversee the government (Twenty first session: 31 December 1930, P.253).

He also requested that the legislative council should be given the right to prosecute and sue members of the executive council. As for the rest of the other articles that members demanded to amend, he indicated that

doesn't agree on either amending or keeping them as they are. (Twenty first session: 31 December, 1930, P 253 – 254).

Nathemy Abed – Alhadi thanked Awdeh Al – Qusous for his statements, because it emphasizes the importance of amending the basic law and asked him to present another formula if he wanted to modify it.

At the end of amending the Basic Law discussion, the chairman turned the proposal of amending the basic Law to the government to formulate the legal formula and obtain opinions. The council approved it by 14 votes against 3 votes. (Twenty first session: 31 December 1930, P.254 – 255).

Later on, some articles of the Basic Law were amended in August, 5 1939. Another amendment was made in March, 16, 1940 (Mahafza, 1937, P.71). However, these amendments didn't comply with the amendments demanded by the members of the first legislative council.

Conclusion:

This study revealed the following results:

- The sessions of the first legislative council revealed the role played by the Christian representatives in severing the legislative process in Transjordan. We found that Awdah Al-Qusous requested Transforming the legislative council into a parliament during the reply to the Royal speech. Awdah Al-Qusous and Najib Abu Al-Shaar had an important role in introducing many amendments to the inner procedure code and obtaining the parliamentary immunity.
- The minutes of the first legislative council session showed the opposition of the Christian representatives to the British administration and its interference in the country affairs. Najib Abu Al-Shaar and Bakhit Al-Ibrahim refused to ratify the Jordanian – British treaty of 1928.
- Christian representatives participated in most of committees that were formed during the first legislative council. Awdeh Al-Qusous and Najib Abu Al-Shaar were chosen in the committee which drafted the reply to the royal speech and in the committee of drafting the inner procedure rules and reviewing the Jordanian – British treaty 1928. That was because of their experience at the political work, their specialization in the legal field, and their proficiency at English language
- The strong opposition of Najib Abu Al-Shaar during the first legislative council was a reason for some of his colleagues to take a position on him in the council, such as Najib Abu Shareda. His criticism of the government, his refusal to ratify the treaty, and his demands to amend the Basic law also caused his continuous clash with Tawfiq Abu Al-Huda the secretary general of the government.

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Author Information

Prof. Ahmad Hamed Ibraheem AlQudah

Professor of Modern History, Department of History
at the College of Arabic Language and Social
Studies, Qassim University . K.S.A.
